

We evaluated the resulting 50 hybrids using a randomized block design with three replications. Each genotype was planted in two 6-m-long rows using a spacing of 20 × 20 cm. Thirty plants per row were maintained. We observed and recorded the important quantitative traits of 20 randomly selected plants in each replication for all hybrids. We subjected the data to analysis of variance and

calculated the combining ability variance.

For all the characters studied (see table) the specific combining ability (SCA) variance was greater than the general combining ability (GCA) variance, indicating the predominance of nonadditive gene action for these traits. This suggests that recurrent selection techniques and diallel selective mating

could be used to improve these traits.

Because rice is a self-pollinated crop, it would be desirable to have multiple crosses and to make selections in the advanced generations and biparental mating for greater genetic improvement. Further, the prevalence of nonadditive gene action implies that all these characters could be improved through heterosis breeding. ■

Identifying japonica-type wide compatibility (JWC) restorers for developing indica/japonica hybrids

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To exploit indica/japonica heterosis, JWC lines have been developed from crosses of WC donor 02428 and japonica cultivars. We crossed 18 JWC lines with two contrasting cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines derived from Hong Lian (HL) and wild abortive (WA) CMS sources to identify JWC restorers that can be used to develop indica/japonica hybrids.

We evaluated the F_1 s for both pollen and spikelet fertility in Nanjing (32° N) in 1990-91.

Seven of the 18 JWC lines are efficient restorers for both HL and WA CMS lines. Another seven are good maintainers for both CMS lines. Of the remaining four testers, JW₅ and JW₁₄ are good restorers for WA CMS lines and maintainers for HL CMS lines. In contrast, JW₁₅ and JW₂₀ are restorers for HL CMS lines and maintainers for WA CMS lines (see table).

Results suggest that of the 18 testers, the seven maintainers for both CMS lines could be used as backcrossing parents to develop WC CMS lines. The seven common restorers could be used to

develop indica/japonica intersubspecific hybrids. Additionally, a partial inverse restorer-maintainer relationship exists between HL and WA CMS lines. This suggests that different Rf gene(s) may exist for restoring fertility to the two CMS lines. If the two CMS sources are used in hybrid rice breeding, the chance of selecting restorers for either of them would increase. ■

The ability of japonica wide compatibility lines to be restorers for HL and/or WA CMS lines. Nanjing, China, 1990-91.

Tester restorer line	Tester CMS source ^a			
	HL		WA	
	Pollen	Seed set	Pollen	Seed set
JW1	F	N	F	N
JW2	CS	PS	S	PS
JW3	F	N	F	N
JW4	F	N	F	N
JW5	S	PS	F	N
JW7	CS	PS	CS	PS
JW8	CS	PS	CS	PS
JW10	F	N	F	N
JW12	CS	PS	CS	PS
JW13	CS	PS	CS	PS
JW14	CS	PS	F	N
JW15	F	N	CS	PS
JW16	F	N	F	N
JW17	CS	PS	CS	PS
JW18	F	N	F	N
JW20	F	N	CS	PS
JW28	CS	PS	CS	PS
1082 R	F	N	F	N

^aF = fertile (>90% pollen fertility), S = sterile (1-30% pollen fertility), CS = completely sterile (<1% pollen fertility), N = normal (>75% seed set), and PS = partially sterile (50% seed set).

Identification of restorers and maintainers for cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) line V20 A

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As research to develop hybrid rice intensifies, an urgent need exists to screen and identify restorers and maintainers for CMS line V20 A.

We crossed V20 A with 89 cultures—locally released varieties and elite and IRRI cultures—and obtained 89 F_1 s at the Regional Research Station (RRS), Mandya, during the 1992 dry season. Hybrids and their parents were transplanted during the following wet season in rows of 30 plants spaced at 15 × 20 cm. Ten plants from each hybrid were labeled. We earmarked three panicles from each plant.

Florets from the upper part of the panicles were collected before flowering. We used KI to stain for pollen fertility. Two panicles from the same plant were bagged before flowering. We calculated spikelet sterility as the percentage of filled grains.

We designated male parents of the hybrids that showed 100% pollen sterility